

FIELD SCREENING OF TOMATO GERMPLASM FOR THE MORPHO-PHYSIOLOGICAL TRAITS IN AUGMENTED BLOCK DESIGN

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Abstract

A field experiment was conducted to assess the performance of tomato germplasm for different morpho-physiological traits in field condition. Seventy-five tomato genotypes (local and exotic) were transplanted in field following augmented complete block design. There were 5 blocks each having 12 genotypes along with three checks i.e., Rio Grande, Roma, Pakit. Data was recorded for plant height, days to flowering, days to maturity, number of flowers per inflorescence, number of inflorescence/plants, Fruit set/ inflorescence, chlorophyll content, yield per plant. For yield/plant trait, ten genotypes have the greater value than these three check genotypes adjusted value in which genotype GSL-198 (1772.78) and LA-1969 (138.11) having greater value and the genotypes 19912 (409.08) and 10165 (470.11) are with less adjusted value than the checks. Maximum number of yields per plant were observed in genotype GSL-198(1782g) and minimum were observed in genotype 19912 (400g). Genotype 17903, 17869 were high yielding while genotype 17903 were recommended for days to maturity, number of flowers per inflorescence.

INTRODUCTION

Tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) is a promising vegetable belongs to nightshade family "Solanaceae". It is the second most important vegetable crop after potato in the world. Being an important commercial and valuable cuisine, widely grown in many countries across the globe. About 4.6 million hectares of tomato are grown worldwide annually with the production of more than 126 million metric tonnes (Campos, Félix, Patanita, Materatski & Varanda, 2021). Apart from its importance, the national average yield of tomato in

Pakistan is 8.4 tons ha⁻¹ (Soomro, Mubarak, & Aqsa, 2020). The average production is incomparable with the average yield of other countries such as China fetching 59.4 tons ha⁻¹ while India (24.6 tons ha⁻¹), USA (96.8 tons ha⁻¹), Turkey (68.8 tons ha⁻¹), and Egypt (40.9 tons ha⁻¹) (Amare & Gebremedhin, 2020). The top ten producing nations are China, India, Turkey, United States, Egypt, Iran, Italy, Spain, Mexico, and Brazil. China is the leading producer with production of 59.5 million tons of tomato having

34.8% share in world tomato production. Pakistan ranked 36 with the production of 0.6 million tons of tomatoes. (FAOSTAT, 2017). These facts and figures showed that per hectare yield of Pakistan is much below the average when compared to its neighboring countries China and India. Number of influences are involved for its low production in the country. The most important and limiting factors are non-availability of high yielding varieties, biotic and abiotic stresses like viruses and diseases (Abdalla, Taha, El-Ramady, & Bayoumi, 2020). Assessment of breeding material for a specific objective is the first aspect of crop improvement program, since it provides the base material for the development of a new variety (Alshaharni, 2025). The present research was conducted to assess the performance of tomato germplasm in field condition and good performing genotypes will be used in further breeding programs.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The experiment was conducted in department of Plant Breeding and Genetics, Arid Agriculture University, Rawalpindi. Seventy-five tomato (*Solanum Lycopersicum* L.) accessions (Table 1.) from National Agriculture Research Centre (NARC), Islamabad, Tomato Genetics Resource Centre (TGRC),

California and Ayub Agricultural Research Institute (AARI), Faisalabad were collected. Due to extreme weather condition and to avoid chilling injury; tomato nursery was kept in glass house and late transplantation was done at the end of March in the field. Seventy-five (75) genotypes were transplanted in field following augmented complete block design. There were 5 blocks each having 12 genotypes along with three checks i.e., Rio Grande, Roma, Pakit. Plants were sown on ridges 75 cm apart having plant to plant distance of 50 cm. The soil of the experimental area was sandy loam in texture having good fertility with 6.7 pH Farmyard manure at the rate of 8-10 tonnes/acre were applied before seedbed preparation. Ridges were prepared for better production. After sowing, N: P: K solution 20:20 :20 was applied in split doses. At anthesis and flower formation stage Potash plus at the rate of 1gm per plant was applied. An amino acid and nutrient-based biostimulant Isabion @ 1ml in 5 litre was also sprayed to enhance crop growth and vigour. Data was recorded for Plant height, days to flowering, days to maturity, number of flowers per inflorescence, number of inflorescence/plant, Fruit set/inflorescence, chlorophyll content, yield per plant .

Table 1: List of tomato germplasm with passport information

Sr No.	Accession	Origin	Sr.No	Name	Origin
1	6231	Exotic	39	NAGINA	Local
2	6233	Exotic	40	ROMA	Local
3	6234	Exotic	41	PAKIT	Local
4	17859	Exotic	42	RIO GRANDE	Local
5	17862	Exotic	43	HT-1914	Exotic
6	17865	Exotic	44	TM-013	Exotic
7	17869	Exotic	45	T-0830	Exotic
8	17870	Exotic	46	SAMRUDHI	Local
9	17889	Exotic	47	T0-1057	Exotic
10	17903	Exotic	48	YAQOOT F1	Exotic
11	19288	Exotic	49	TTM-502	Exotic
12	19289	Exotic	50	RANI	Exotic
13	19291	Exotic	51	TEJAS	Exotic
14	19292	Exotic	52	KANWAL	Exotic
15	19887	Exotic	53	TM-1826	Exotic
16	19890	Exotic	54	QASBA F1	Exotic
17	19892	Exotic	55	INDIGO F1	Exotic
18	19893	Exotic	56	FOSTER	Exotic

19	19904	Exotic	57	GSL-198	Exotic
20	19912	Exotic	58	BPVT-15-1	Exotic
21	27648	Exotic	59	17878	Exotic
22	29448	Exotic	60	17909	Exotic
23	29467	Exotic	61	10158	Exotic
24	29471	Exotic	62	LA-1969	Exotic
25	29508	Exotic	63	19893	Exotic
26	29510	Exotic	64	10122	Exotic
27	29522	Exotic	65	317790	Exotic
28	29628	Exotic	66	10196	Exotic
29	CBS-292	Exotic	67	10108	Exotic
30	AGATA	Exotic	68	10148	Exotic
31	WANTIA F1	Exotic	69	10132	Exotic
32	KANON F1	Exotic	70	10165	Exotic
33	BPVT-14-1	Exotic	71	10138	Exotic
34	ROSHAN F1	Exotic	72	10104	Exotic
35	HT-1570 F1	Exotic	73	10109	Exotic
36	KORTAJA F1	Exotic	74	10145	Exotic
37	NADIR Local	75	10111	Exotic	
38	NAQEEB	Local	10194	Exotic	

Statistical Analysis

ANOVA for remaining parameters sown in augmented block design were obtained using SAS software.

The statistical model for the augmented design is

$$Y_{ij} = \mu + \tau_i + e_{ij} ; i=1, 2, \dots, v, v+c \text{ and } j=1, 2, \dots, b.$$

Where

Y_{ij} = observation of treatment i in j th block;

μ = general mean

τ_i = effect of treatment i (test treatment and control treatment);

ρ_j =the effects of j th block and

e_{ij} = residual variation or error

Block adjustment $a_j = X_j - X$

Where X_j = Mean of allchecks in the j th block

X = Grand mean of all checks.

In Augmented design the experimental error is estimated considering the controls placed in randomized complete block design. After conducting the analysis of the controls, the error mean square from this analysis is used to compute the standard errors for different comparisons; the different between the mean of the controls in a given block and the mean of the controls over the entire experiment.

$$S_{vc} = \sqrt{((r+1)(c+1)MSE)/rc}$$

Where

S_{vc} = Difference between adjusted yield of new selection and check means

r = Number of blocks

c =Number of different checks per block

Results and Discussions

1.Plant height

Analysis of variance (ANOVA) for plant height revealed significant variation among seventy-five tomato accessions (Table 2.). Plant height varied from 30cm (genotype TM-1826) to 120cm (genotype 29448) with a grand mean value of 71.4cm. The coefficient of variability (CV%) for plant height was 24% (Table 3).For the comparison of mean performance of genotypes against three checks, an adjusted value for plant height are calculated and given in Table 4. There are fifty-eight genotypes which have the greater value than these three check genotypes adjusted value in which 29448 (123.1), 19892 (113.1) and 27648 (107.4) having greater value and the genotypes TM-1826 (31.1) and 19288 (34.3) are with less adjusted value. Tomato plant can grow to various sizes depending upon its growth habit. Determinate types stop in increase in height after specific phase of growth while indeterminate are vine type and grow very tall. For tunnel farming

indeterminate types were used. As genotypes used in present study were both determinate and indeterminate so a wide range of variability exist for this trait. In Pakistan, tomato mostly grown outdoor in open field so determinate types were preferred for field cultivation. Plants height in tomato crop is

associated with high yield (Ara, Narayan, Ahmed & Khan, 2009) so genotypes with tall growth are important in yield improvement. In tomato both determinate and indeterminate genotypes are present. For field sowing plant with determinate habit are recommended.

Table 2.: Mean squares values from ANOVA for morpho/physiological traits in tomato accessions

SOV	D.F	Pl. height	Days to flo.	Days to mat.	No. of flowers/inf.	No. of inf/pl.	Fruit set/inf.	Chl.c	Yield
Blocks	4	9.51	2.8	6.34	0.15	0.439	0.48 *	0.001	1757
Checks	2	450.9*	39.6*	5.54	1.5 *	1.768*	0.99*	3.24**	103613 *
Varieties	71	247.2*	20.0*	25.043*	7.9**	5.26**	2.19**	0.58**	83945**
Error	8	10.9	2.08	10.277	0.112	0.292	0.12	0.007	5905.7

Where

Days to flo. = days to flowering

Days to mat. =Days to maturity

No. of flowers/inf.=Number of flowers per inflorescence

No. of inf/pl.= Number of inflorescences per plant

Fruit set/inf.=Fruit set per inflorescence Chl.c=chlorophyll contents

Table 3: Grand mean, range and coefficient of variation (CV%) for morpho/physiological traits

Trait	Grand mean	CV%	Range
Plant height (cm)	71.4	24.3	30-120
Days to flowering	57	5.17	51-64
Days to maturity	177	2.5	168-185
Number of flowers per inflorescence	8	17.4	5 - 12.6
Number of fruits set per inflorescence	5	18.3	3.6 - 9.6
Number of inflorescence per plant	8	20	4.6 - 11.7
Yield/Plant (g)	909	25.8	400 - 1782
Chlorophyll Contents (µg/ml)	27	23	13.5 - 40

2. Days to flowering

Analysis of variance (ANOVA) for days to flowering revealed significant variation among seventy-five tomato accessions (Table 2). Days to flowering varied from 51 (17903) to 64 days (SAMRUDHI) with a grand mean value of 57 days. The coefficient of variability (CV%) for days to flowering was 5.1% (Table3). There are seventeen genotypes which have the greater value than these three check genotypes adjusted value in which SAMRUDHI (65.42) and

ROSHAN F1(64.02) having greater value and the genotypes 17903(49.8) and 19292(51.22) are with less adjusted value then the checks (Table 4). Lesser days to flowering is desirable. Early flowering in tomatoes has dual advantages. First, early flowering provides more time for seed maturation which leads to yield improvement. On the other hand, it also escapes crop from chilling stress in case of September sowing of this crop.

Table 4: Adjusted performance of checks and tomato accessions for Morpho-physiological Traits (pl.height= plant height, Days to flo.=days to flowering, Days to mat.=days to maturity, No of fl/inf= number of flower/ inflorescence, Fruit set/inf= fruit set per inflorescence, No of inf/pl= number of inflorescence/ plant, Yield/pl= yield /plant, Chlo con= chlorophyll content)from augmented design

Sr No	Genotypes	Blocks	Pl.height	Days to flo.	Days to mat.	No of fl/inf	Fruit set/inf	No of inf/pl	Yield/pl	Chlo con.
1	6231	1	79.3	53.22	169.4	8.08	8.456	10.242	1016.41	26.0
2	6233	1	66.7	52.22	174.4	6.92	7.356	10.242	694.913	24.8
3	6234	1	83.0	52.52	183.4	7.62	8.056	12.942	725.313	38.6
4	17859	1	65.3	57.82	174.1	6.18	7.556	10.242	734.913	28.3
5	17862	1	78.3	52.82	179.4	8.18	8.556	6.942	894.713	13.8
6	17865	1	64.3	56.52	181.4	7.82	15.256	4.942	694.71	25.6
7	17869	1	46.3	58.52	182.4	5.12	5.556	5.942	1004.91	13.7
8	17870	1	89.0	57.22	180.4	5.72	6.156	6.642	695.013	32.9
9	17889	1	53.7	54.82	178.8	9.72	10.156	8.942	1205.61	22.8
10	17903	1	37.0	49.82	167.8	12.72	6.856	5.642	1318.21	33.6
11	19288	1	34.3	55.22	184.4	8.92	15.356	13.242	1204.71	23.6
12	19289	1	63.7	55.82	182.8	6.12	6.556	7.942	724.713	19.8
13	19291	1	78.3	58.82	183.4	7.08	7.456	6.242	847.713	15.7
14	19292	1	93.3	51.22	177.4	10.22	10.656	12.242	1118.713	24.7
15	19887	2	93.4	54.42	177.7	7.39	9.256	11.372	1118.08	29.8
16	19890	2	45.4	55.12	171.7	8.06	7.856	5.372	609.08	20.6
17	19892	2	113.1	56.72	175.7	11.02	10.856	13.072	709.08	28.7
18	19893	2	104.7	53.42	182.7	11.52	11.356	11.372	1343.68	27.1
19	19904	2	65.7	54.42	180.7	7.99	8.856	5.072	489.78	19.7
20	19912	2	97.1	52.72	178.7	9.96	19.756	11.072	409.08	26.8
21	27648	2	107.4	57.42	181.7	8.06	7.856	10.372	729.08	25.6
22	29448	2	123.1	53.12	174.7	7.89	7.756	11.372	659.08	29.8
23	29467	2	87.1	54.42	173.7	8.22	12.056	10.072	709.08	31.4
24	29471	2	85.1	57.42	184.7	6.36	10.156	6.072	547.08	22.7
25	29508	2	82.1	54.72	177.4	10.69	17.556	5.372	761.08	29.8
26	29510	2	101.1	58.72	175.7	10.62	14.456	5.072	692.08	23.5
27	29522	2	67.4	60.12	178.7	9.36	13.156	7.372	509.08	22.6
28	29628	2	105.7	56.72	176.7	9.86	11.656	9.672	774.08	37.6
29	CBS-292	3	72.9	55.42	177.7	5.19	10.386	11.142	835.48	25.2
30	AGATA	3	56.2	58.72	167.7	10.42	10.686	11.142	1161.48	33.2
31	WANTIA F1	3	84.2	56.72	175.4	8.85	11.086	5.842	1105.48	25.9
32	KANON F1	3	62.5	56.72	182.0	7.72	7.986	8.842	1155.48	36.2
33	BPVT-14-1	3	80.9	60.72	178.0	6.95	7.186	7.842	965.48	20.9
34	ROSHAN F1	3	62.2	64.02	175.0	8.65	8.886	11.142	1056.48	29.1
35	HT-1570 F1	3	73.5	58.72	171.0	6.75	9.986	7.142	935.48	27.8
36	KORTAJA F1	3	75.9	57.72	173.7	7.22	10.486	7.842	1105.48	26.1
37	NADIR	3	60.2	52.72	177.0	6.89	7.086	9.142	1005.48	20.8
38	NAQEEB	3	70.5	57.02	170.0	7.39	8.586	7.842	1135.48	28.4
39	NAGINA	3	63.2	58.02	171.7	7.45	8.686	8.142	1220.78	17.7
40	HT-1914	3	65.2	60.72	175.0	7.45	7.686	7.842	1081.18	14.3
41	TM-013	3	54.2	55.42	178.0	6.22	6.486	8.442	874.38	21.8
42	T-0830	3	62.2	60.42	176.0	9.45	9.686	10.842	835.48	26.4
43	SAMRUDHI	3	51.2	65.42	176.0	7.69	11.886	7.442	750.48	22.3

44	TO-1057	4	71.1	55.62	181.7	9.85	9.744	11.872	825.78	21.1
45	YAQOOT F1	4	60.7	54.62	176.0	9.95	9.844	12.472	1206.78	31.7
46	TM- 502	4	42.4	61.32	176.4	5.89	8.744	7.472	822.78	27.0
47	RANI	4	49.4	58.62	171.7	7.35	7.244	11.872	1246.78	29.6
48	TEJAS	4	56.1	54.62	179.0	7.79	7.644	8.172	810.78	31.6
49	KANWAL	4	73.7	58.92	182.4	10.00	9.944	11.172	1068.78	20.7
50	TM-1826	4	31.1	61.62	172.0	9.92	20.844	8.172	775.78	21.3
51	QASBA F1	4	64.1	57.62	174.7	9.52	9.444	10.472	910.78	21.8
52	INDIGO F1	4	86.4	62.62	173.4	7.85	9.744	10.172	1205.78	22.1
53	FOSTER	4	80.7	60.62	179.4	7.62	7.544	4.872	690.78	21.1
54	GSL-198	4	76.1	53.62	176.0	8.02	7.944	11.172	1772.78	40.1
55	BPVT-15-1	4	59.7	55.62	173.0	7.22	7.144	8.872	965.68	23.8
56	17878	4	79.1	61.62	178.0	8.92	8.844	6.872	604.08	40.0
57	10158	4	73.4	54.62	182.0	8.62	8.544	11.472	964.38	28.8
58	LA-1969	5	70.0	57.72	176.7	10.59	14.156	7.372	1380.113	29.9
59	19893	5	92.3	54.72	170.1	9.02	9.956	11.672	1010.113	38.0
60	10122	5	46.3	59.72	175.7	7.96	7.456	9.372	870.113	16.4
61	317790	5	78.0	61.02	179.1	8.12	7.656	6.072	820.113	25.0
62	10196	5	69.3	57.72	173.7	6.69	6.256	7.672	570.113	32.9
63	10108	5	62.7	62.72	173.7	5.76	6.256	6.672	753.113	21.0
64	10148	5	77.3	56.42	179.7	7.16	6.656	9.072	590.113	32.0
65	10132	5	63.3	56.72	176.7	5.59	8.156	5.372	615.113	31.1
66	10165	5	75.7	57.72	183.1	7.42	6.956	7.072	470.113	21.1
67	10138	5	66.0	60.72	182.7	7.56	7.056	9.672	793.113	24.3
68	10104	5	67.0	61.72	182.1	6.46	5.956	8.072	690.113	33.1
69	10109	5	81.3	59.72	184.7	6.59	6.156	6.072	1070.113	36.9
70	10111	5	78.0	58.72	175.7	6.99	6.556	4.072	870.113	33.7
71	10194	5	76.7	63.02	176.7	7.79	7.356	7.672	751.013	34.7
72	10145	5	62.0	59.22	174.7	7.52	8.056	6.672	1100.113	33.2
73	Rio Grande	Check1	69.78	60.94	184.6	7.345	6.27	7.99	1678.156	22.12
74	Roma	Check2	59.56	56.2	186.42	6.645	6.215	8.71	1267.296	30.62
75	Pakit	Check3	74.97	61.2	184.5	7.725	7.015	9.17	1202.956	34.32

3. Days to maturity

Analysis of variance (ANOVA) for days to maturity revealed significant variation among seventy-five tomato accessions (Table 2). Days to maturity varied from 168 to 185 days with a grand mean value of 177 days. The coefficient of variability (CV%) for days to maturity was 2.5% (Table 3). From table 4 it is clear that there are three genotypes which have the greater value than these three check genotypes adjusted value in which genotype 10109 ,29471(184.7) and19288(184.4) having greater value and the genotypes AGATA (167.7) and 17903(167.8) are with less adjusted value then the checks. Genotypes 10109 and 29471 took maximum days to maturity 184.7,

while genotype 17903 took minimum days to maturity 168.3 days. Early maturing genotypes have advantage of less utilization of crop production resources and give more profit to farmers in form of early marketing and off-season production. On the other hand, it was reported that days to maturity has direct negative effect of yield of tomato plant (Saleem, Iqbal & Asghar,2013).

4. Number of flowers per inflorescence

Highly significant difference among genotypes was observed for the number of flowers per inflorescence from ANOVA (Table 2). Number of flowers per inflorescence ranges from 5 to 12.6 with a grand mean

of 8. Coefficient of variability (CV %) for number of flowers per inflorescence was 17% (Table 3). For the comparison of mean performance of genotypes against three Check varieties Rio Grande, Roma, Pakit adjusted values for days to maturity were calculated (Table 4). There are fifty-five genotypes which have the greater value than these three check genotypes adjusted value in which genotype 17903(12.72) and 19893 (11.52) having greater value and the genotypes 17869(5.12) and CBS-292(5.19) are with less adjusted value than the checks. Maximum number of flowers per inflorescence were observed in genotype 17903(12.7) and minimum were observed in genotype 17869(5).

5. Fruit set per inflorescence

Fruit set per inflorescence shows highly significant difference among genotypes that was observed from ANOVA (Table 2). It ranges from 3.6 to 9.6. having the grand mean of 5. Coefficient of variability (CV %) for fruit set per inflorescence was 18.3% (Table 3). Adjusted values for fruit set per inflorescence were calculated (Table 4) to compare the mean performance of genotypes against three Check varieties viz., Rio Grande, Roma, Pakit. There are sixty-eight genotypes which have the greater value than these three check genotypes adjusted value in which genotype TM-1826(20.844) and 29508 (17.556) having greater value and the genotypes 17869(5.556) and 10104(5.956) are with less adjusted value than the checks. Maximum fruit set per inflorescence were observed in genotype LA-1969(9.7) and minimum were observed in genotype RANI and 17869(3.7).

6. Number of inflorescences per plant

Highly significant difference among genotypes was observed for the number of inflorescence per plant from ANOVA (Table 2). Number of inflorescences per plant ranges from 4.6 to 11.7 with a grand mean of 8. Coefficient of variability (CV %) for number of inflorescence per plant was 20% (Table 3). There are forty-three genotypes which have the greater value than these three check genotypes adjusted value in which genotype 19288(13.24) and 19292 (12.24) having greater value and the genotypes 10111(4.07) and FOSTER (4.87) are with less adjusted value than the checks. Maximum number of inflorescence per plant was observed in genotype TO-1057(11.7) and

minimum were observed in genotype 10111,19904 and 29510(4.7) (Table 4)

7. Yield per plant (g)

Yield from the ANOVA (Table 2.) revealed highly significant difference among genotypes. Yield ranges from 400 to 1782(g) with a grand mean of 909(g). Coefficient of variability (CV %) for number of inflorescence per plant was 25.8% (Table 3). To compare the mean performance of genotypes against three Check varieties Rio Grande, Roma, Pakit adjusted values for yield were calculated (Table 4). There are ten genotypes which have the greater value than these three check genotypes adjusted value in which genotype GSL-198 (1772.78) and LA-1969 (138.11) having greater value and the genotypes 19912 (409.08) and 10165 (470.11) are with less adjusted value than the checks. Maximum number of yields per plant were observed in genotype GSL-198(1782g) and minimum were observed in genotype 19912 (400g).

Tomato is very sensitive crop in relation to temperature and sunlight. Temperature has a large effect on all aspects of growth and development in tomato. Leaf and truss initiation severely effected with decreasing temperature. Despite of variation in varietal response the effect of low temperature on this crop is same. Fruit setting is also reduced due to poor pollen quality in low temperature (Zheng, Yang, Wei, & Zhao, 2022). Low yield in tomato in this research is due to fluctuation in temperature in rawalpindi.

8. Total chlorophyll contents

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for total chlorophyll contents revealed significant variation among seventy-five tomato accessions (Table 2). Total chlorophyll contents varied from 13.5 to 40 with a grand mean value of 27. The coefficient of variability (CV%) for total chlorophyll contents was 23% (Table 3). Comparison of mean performance (Table 4) identify fifty-two genotypes which have the greater value than these three check genotypes adjusted value in which genotype GSL-198(40.1) and 17878 (40) having greater value and the genotypes 17869(13.7) and 17862(13.8) are with less adjusted value than the checks. Genotype 6234 contains maximum total chlorophyll contents 40 and minimum total chlorophyll contents 13.6 lies in genotype HT-1914.

Conclusion

Seventy-five local and exotic tomato accessions were screened for different morpho-physiological trait. Genotypes TM -1826,10145, SAMRUDHI, Rio grande recommended for higher yield, fruit set per inflorescence and but low in chlorophyll content. Genotype like GSL-198, 10109, !7903, 29467, LA-1969 were recommended for tall height, high number of flower /inflorescence, high chlorophyll content and yield. These genotypes will be used in future breeding program in developing high yielding cultivars.

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